

HISTORY OF SOLAR ARCHITECTURE IN CYPRUS

Petros A. Lapithis
e-mail: lapithis.p@intercollege.ac.cy

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to document the design and construction of buildings in our human heritage approaching it from a solar design point of view. Elements, which are now fundamentally used in passive architecture, can be found in constructions created since 7000B.C. These examples, illustrate strong characteristics of historical architecture, which serve as fine examples of energy-saving architecture today. As such, the paper does not attempt a complete historical or geographic analysis of the entire range of building forms. Yet, by selectively looking at examples of buildings we see that there are important linking attitudes and unavoidable laws of physical performance. We have access a surprisingly rich and complex vocabulary of forms and principles. Cypriot traditional houses have proved to be superiorly energy-efficient (243 kWh/m² annual energy use) when compared to contemporary houses (368 kWh/m²) due to the thermal performance of both cases based on their architectural design.

1. INTRODUCTION

In those climates, like Cyprus where hot days alternate with cool nights, we find a characteristic building form that takes advantage of the heat-retention qualities of heavy masonry. The thickness of the walls is a factor of the material used and the temperature differential and range found at that location. In all these hot climates, since the roof is the main recipient of the full impact of the midday sun, construction techniques have been developed to permit it to have heat-retention characteristics similar to the walls. Limited wall openings affect the retention of more heat for release at night. The entire structure is in delicate balance. The characteristics described are typical, and as with all typical phenomena, there are exceptions.

2. NEOLITHIC AGE (7000-3900 BC)

2.1 Khirokitia¹

Many of these Neolithic structures exhibit insulated walls and can be considered as passive solar techniques (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Khirokitia village

The basic architectural unit was a structure with a circular ground plan, the exterior diameter of which varies between 2.3 and 9.2m and the interior diameter between 1.4 and 4.8m with doorways 0.5m wide opening onto an uncovered space. Each of these units, with their diverse internal arrangements, was part of a larger domestic space: the house. Its ideal form may be defined as a compound of several of these circular units around an unroofed space, a kind of small inner “courtyard”.

The materials used were stone-blocks of light-coloured limestone collected on the surface and dark diabase pebbles from the river-bed-pise and mud brick, made from earth mixed with straw and dried in the sun. These materials were used either singly or in combination with each other. Walls were made of stones set on one or two courses and bonded with mud mortar. Mud brick or pise walls were made of stones embedded in pise. Walls were even built in two concentric rings, the outer one of stones, and the inner one of pise or mud bricks, the latter sometimes resting on a

stone substructure. A whitish earth plaster covers the internal and external faces of the wall. Flat stones, set on edge around the base of the wall would sometimes protect it from erosion by rainwater.

2.2 Kalavassos

The diameter of the domestic structures varies from 2.40m to 3.60m. These constructions are similar to Khirokitia. The configuration of the superstructure of the buildings and the nature of their roofs have been debated at length. The inward curvature of some of the walls has been taken to indicate the existence of domed roofs, and past reconstructions of Khirokitia have shown all of the domestic building with domed roofs. The frequent occurrence of basically vertical walls without any trace of inward inclination would seem to indicate flat roofs (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Two alternative roof reconstructions

3. 2000BC – MID 20TH CENTURY

Approximately since 2000 BC, until the mid 20th century AD, construction methods have varied only slightly². The same building material such as wooden beams, straw, clay mixtures and stones were used in approximate methods.

In most of the Cypriot traditional architecture there is much wisdom in the method of construction and for the most part, the solutions found and utilised are both ingenious and economic. The buildings are designed and constructed to

fully exploit advantages offered by the local climatic conditions and are characterised by:

- The positions in orientation to the sun path either to avoid direct sunlight entering the building or the opposite.
- The exploitation of breezes for ventilation and cross ventilation in the room
- The awareness and exploitation of the nature of flora and its use for practical functions (e.g. medicinal plants)
- A good insulation of walls (40-50cm width) and roofs,
- Small openings on the external walls for maximum insulation.

Most of the rural type houses had only one floor, but two storey houses were sometimes constructed. The houses were usually smaller in size than the town type, with limited openings, and the development of the villages was compact due to reasons of defence and lack of available space. In most cases there is a courtyard in front of the house, and where there is not, the flat roofs were used for open-space activities. Stairs leading to the upper floor were either external made from stone, or internal from timber. Tracing the evolution of indigenous Cypriot architecture, an archetypal form of a single, long, rectangular roomed building called 'Makrinari' (long room) is revealed as the simplest basic shelter in Cyprus (Fig. 3). It is generally south oriented with its long axis along the East-West direction. Then the division of this room called 'Dhichoron' (double space), the addition of other rooms called 'Sospiton' (inner room) and a covered veranda called 'Iliakos' (solarium) were placed.

1. Makrinari
2. Dhichoron
3. Inner room
4. Inner room
5. Iliakos
6. Traditional earth oven.
7. Courtyard.

Fig. 3: Rural type house

Due to its orientation and the mild weather conditions of the plain, the 'iliakos' was used as a sitting room, cooking place and generally as a working place. The Solarium is an indispensable solar feature of the Cypriot house. It was an

early instinctive approach to passive solar design. Its solar role was predominant whether acting as an arched corridor, as a central axis or even when it evolved into a self-contained space. The introduction of the permanent solarium overhang on the fenestration of Cypriot houses, results to a reduction of heating saving only by 8%.³ This is attributed to the loss of useful solar gains intercepted by the permanent solarium overhangs. However the summer shading benefits are exceedingly more to justify the incorporation of solariums on the houses facades.

Later this type of house was developed into a multi-room house, by adding extra rooms to the east or west of 'Makrinari' plus the courtyard. These additions sometimes kept the rectangular shape of the house but others led to the L-shape⁴ Despite these changes to the general layout of the house, the south facing 'iliakos' facing the courtyard did not change.

The courtyard is an arrangement that evolved naturally from the climatic conditions, the needs of the family and the social structure of the community. It generally creates a microclimate that moderates the climate surrounding the building. Planted mostly with deciduous vegetation like grapevines, fig trees etc, it offers shade in the summer and admits sun in the winter. It also creates windy sides that are most valuable when one seeks the breeze in the summer and calm corners in the winter. Arched arcades at the perimeter are indispensable to shield the overhead midday sun⁵. Studies carried out amongst Cypriot houses, with and without courtyards, it was found that introduction of courtyards and south facing windows incur more savings.⁶

All the openings were placed to the south wall to provide natural light and heat. The construction of those openings was made entirely by wood. Small openings called 'arseres' were also used in every house (Fig.4). These were placed at the upper part of the walls. In summer, they allowed lighter hot air to go out of the house and be replaced by cooler air from outside, while in winter, thymes (small dense bushes) were closing these openings and they provided thermal insulation.

Fig. 4: "arseres"
External and internal walls were made from stone, usually schist, without connecting material. They are plastered inside with sand and lime mortar while the external side is unplastered and whitewashed in most cases.

Roofs were usually flat. The construction method is as follows: first a framework of timber beams is constructed, which is then covered with schist, clay tiles or reeds. Over these, seaweed or other plants are set and finally the construction is completed with a thick layer of soil that provides insulation. In some rural areas where timber does not exist at all, roofs are stone vaulted constructions. In some cases the vault is visible externally and in others is covered with soil.

Floors between storeys were made from timber and ground floors were usually paved.

4. COLONIAL PERIOD

Designing an effective scheme to provide natural ventilation was a crucial consideration in early colonial architecture⁷ in Cyprus. The scheme had separate arrangements for fresh air intake and foul air exhaust, usually one set per habitable room. Fresh air was admitted through the exterior building wall near the ceiling of each room through perforated terracotta or cast iron grills on the outside surface, and came into the room through adjustable wooden louvers placed on the inside surface (Fig.5 and Fig. 6). This bioclimatic technic passed foul air through wooden grills on an interior wall and rose naturally via terracotta pipes within the interior wall, and was then expelled into the prevailing breeze above the roof.

Fig. 5: Buildings for Cyprus Pioneers: details of ventilation system.

Fig. 6: Section of Offices for Cyprus Pioneers. The two rows of rooms are set back-to-back, sharing a common interior wall. This wall supports the roof and carries six ventilation pipes inside it, each 22.5cm in diameter and leading to exhaust vents in a single chimney-like structure rising above the roof, visible in the elevation on the opposite page.

Colonial architecture has influenced the built environment and attitudes of Cypriots to a great extent. All the private buildings built by Cypriots in those years were designed in a very clean and simple way, which did not impinge on the environment or the viewer. Elements in Cypriot architecture such as the rounded form of the dining room, the symmetrical roof, and the round ventilator in the gable are common to both colonial and domestic architecture in Cyprus.

5. CONTEMPORARY PERIOD

The types of traditional houses described were constructed up until the beginning of the 20th century. Later, with the introduction of contemporary architectural practices in Cyprus, a different construction approach began. Before the Cypriot independence in 1960, specialized building tradesmen constructed dwellings. In particular, the existence of itinerant building teams is very important because as they moved from place to place, they learned a lot from local architecture and influenced the method of construction and building types in other regions. Furthermore, local people began to travel abroad and influence construction by bringing prototypes from many countries.

The Turkish Invasion of Cyprus in 1974 brought a deep economic crisis and 200 thousand refugees, which were uprooted from their land in north Cyprus by the Turkish troops. Architects were forced to consider architecture as a social science rather than a fine art. These years were a period when it was necessary to understand social problems and to search for an appropriate architecture to deal with them.

Government housing was designed to be constructed quickly to relieve the burden of refugees living in tents.

Although quickly and cheaply constructed, these homes satisfy basic needs like a shaded porch area and a solar heater for hot water.

The housing problem in Southern Cyprus was immediately dealt with by government's initiative and action, beginning with the reconstruction of destroyed areas to alleviate the housing shortage in the cities. As a result, the housing problem passed into the hands of private businessmen, first in Lefkosia and then in other cities. In fact, because of the absence of other investments, the building industry began to play a determining role in shaping the Cypriot economy. As a result, private building construction boomed during this period.

Despite the interests of many Cypriot architects in traditional and solar architecture, who certainly consider the climate, the majority of Cypriot designers tend to ignore it. Contemporary life and the building industry in Cyprus are greatly affected by the proliferation of apartment blocks in the large urban centres. The apartment house became the symbol of the final stage of urbanisation. And since urbanisation is the ideal way of living for the contemporary Cypriot, the apartment model is adopted everywhere even in the small single houses at the most underdeveloped areas of the country.

Three categories of construction financing have been developed. In the first, a contractor undertakes the construction of the building. In the second, the owner of the property decides to play the role of the contractor-entrepreneur and undertakes the responsibility of constructing and financing the project. He/she usually sells or rents most of the apartments keeping one or two for him/her. In the third (the gradual method of construction), the owner of the property builds one housing unit for the present needs of his/her family, allowing for the possibility of constructing additional apartments in the future to cover the needs of the growing family or merely for investment reasons. The results of this practice in the form of the city are the following:

- o Lack of planned connection between housing areas and other areas of the city (educational, commercial, etc)
- o Mixed housing areas with industrial or other areas, dangerous for public health
- o Very limited green and open spaces within the housing areas
- o Bad relation between street width and building height.
- o Different housing types even in the same street-large apartment blocks adjacent to low houses.⁸
- o Unplanned and often unhealthy interaction between the built and natural environment.

In an analysis of the built environment of the city area,⁹ it was concluded that the negative points of the housing

environment are not due to the lack of adequate housing units, but to the use of the continuous construction system, the high ratio of building area to site area. This results in the lack of open spaces and to the quality of the immediate environment around the houses with the result of little nature light and ventilation, no solar access etc.

6. CONTEMPORARY VS TRADITIONAL VS SOLAR

Thermal performance of traditional, contemporary and solar houses have been researched in relation to climate and in terms of the various aspects necessary for understanding such performances¹⁰. These aspects include architectural design, constructional materials and methods, occupancy patterns and planning. Different architectural and constructional elements and techniques that were used in traditional houses are studied in relation to their use in passive design today and serve as fine examples of energy-saving architecture.

Cypriot traditional houses have proved to be superiorly energy-efficient (243kWh/m²) when compared to contemporary houses (368 kWh/m²) resulting to the most energy efficient being a passive solar house (121 kWh/m²) due to the thermal performance of all cases based on their architectural design. Taking into account the general characteristics of the dry climate and the requirements it imposes on the house characteristics and the general characteristics and thermal performance of traditional and contemporary houses, it may be concluded that traditional houses in Cyprus meet the requirements imposed by the climate and that these houses are good enough thermally to perform well under the prevailing weather conditions. Because of Cyprus climate, passive solar architecture works to its full capacity.

7. CONCLUSION

In urban and architectural studies, of Cyprus, one should never neglect early practices. Man has always striven to build his dwellings in order to attain optimum conditions of comfort. In all cases, man has found some fairly good and some excellent solutions. Close examination of buildings in Cyprus gives rise to some questions about these solutions, however. The task of a designer or a researcher is to question, to determine problems, and to search for contemporary solutions.

The most impressive characteristics found in each of these historical examples discussed show variety and inventiveness. Each solution accurately reflects the available materials, the specific local climate, and the special role the building is expected to play. Examples can be added almost

without end, showing how building form responded to all these conditions, how building material selection and use aided this performance, and how each shift necessitated a series of other changes to establish a new balance in the building's performance.

Elements, which are now fundamentally used in passive architecture, can be found in constructions created since 9000B.C. These examples, illustrate strong characteristics of historical architecture, which serve as fine examples of energy-saving architecture today and are used on the Experimental Solar House. Early examples include:

- o The Solarium was predominant whether acting as an arched corridor, as a central axis or even when it evolved into a self-contained space.
- o Courtyards, planted mostly with deciduous vegetation like grapevines, providing shade in the summer and admitting the sun in the winter
- o Almost all openings placed on the south wall providing natural light and heat.
- o Arseres allowed lighter hot air to go out of the house and be replaced by cooler air from outside in the summer
- o Thymes (small dense bushes) blocked the arseres in the winter and provided thermal insulation.
- o Roofs and floors were constructed in a typical insulating manner
- o Courtyards were built to facing southwards, acting as a sunspace, receiving desired solar radiation in winter.
- o The solarium admits the rays from the winter sun to penetrate and so solar radiation could be utilised in winter.
- o In multiple thermal modes and varied design, the courtyard and the solarium moderate high summer temperatures- their careful construction combined with the surrounding landscaping lower the temperatures around the house.
- o Clear topographical clarifications
- o The positions in orientation to the sun path either to avoid direct sunlight entering the house of the opposite.
- o The exploitation of breezes for ventilation and cross ventilation in the room
- o The awareness and exploitation of the nature of flora and its use for practical functions (e.g. medicinal plants, fruit-bearing trees)
- o A good insulation of walls (30-40cm width) and roofs,
- o The small openings on the external walls for maximum insulation (north, east, west).

Architects, critics, and consumers have been questioning the way in which professionals in Cyprus have been planning and building recently, particularly in connection with how the buildings perform as energy-consuming entities. In previous times there was an inseparable interrelationship

between the purposes of buildings and their forms. These forms are the product and expression of principles that still apply. By indoctrinating ourselves with the principles rather than the forms, we can learn from the past. The programmatic demands - the listing of spaces for different activities and occupants within buildings - vary enormously from building to building. Response to these demands, coupled with the regional climatic and local microclimatic conditions and the site characteristics can lead to a rewarding richness and variety without having to depend on the multiplication of materials, the application of surface textures for diversions, and similar cosmetic devices.

8. REFERENCES

¹ A. Le Brun, "Khirokitia, A Neolithic Site", Bank of Cyprus Cultural Foundation in collaboration with the department of Antiquities, Lefkosia, Cyprus, 1997.

² P. Lapithis, "Solar Architecture in Cyprus". Proceedings ISES Conference, Gotheburg, Sweden. 19-22 July 2003.

³ D. Serghides, 'The Solarium and the courtyard as climatic modifiers in Mediterranean Vernacular Architecture', Proceedings of the 1st World Renewable Energy Congress, Reading, UK, *Technology and the Environment*, vol. 4, pp 23-28 September 1990, pp 1752-1764.

⁴ S. Sinou, "Anadromi sti Laiki Architectoniki, (Retrospection in Folk Architecture)", 1976, Athens, p.47, p.53.

⁵ E. Fernandes, S. Yannas, "Energy and Buildings for Temperate Climates - A Mediterranean Regional Approach", Proceedings of the PLEA 88 Conference, 1998, Porto, Pergamon Press, Oxford.

⁶ D. Serghides, "The Solarium and the courtyard as climatic modifiers in Mediterranean Vernacular Architecture", Proceedings of the 1st World Renewable Energy Congress, Reading, UK, *Technology and the Environment*, vol. 4, pp 23-28 September 1990, pp 1752-1764.

⁷ K. Schaar, M. Given, G. Theocharous, "Under the clock-Colonial Architecture and history in Cyprus", Bank of Cyprus, Nicosia, 1995.

⁸ A. Aravantinos, "Urban Planning, Part II. House and City", 1984, National Technical University of Athens.

⁹ Sariyannis et al, "Research on urban planning prototypes: housing", 1977, National Technical University of Athens.

¹⁰ Lapithis, P. "Traditional vs Contemporary vs Solar Buildings". Proceedings ISES Conference, Freiburg, Germany. 19-22 July 2004.